

Metal Derivatives of Organo-Phosphorus Compounds. Part II : Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) Derivatives

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Reactions between niobium(V) chloride, tantalum(V) chloride and dialkyl/diaryl (Et-, Pr^t-, Buⁿ- and Ph-) phosphites have been studied in different molar ratios and under different conditions of temperature and solvent systems. The complex compounds of the type $MCl_5[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (I); $MCl_4[OP(O)(OR)][P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (II); $MCl_3[OP(O)(OR)]_2[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (III); $MCl_2[P(O)(OR)]_3[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (IV); $MCl[OP(O)(OR)]_4[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (V); $M[OP(O)(OR)]_5[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (VI); $MCl[P(O)(OR)]_6[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (VII); $M[OP(O)(OR)]_7[OP(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (VIII) and $M[P(O)(OR)]_8[P(O)(OR)_2]_n$, (IX) (M=Nb or Ta and R=Et-, Pr^t-, Buⁿ- or Ph-) have been isolated. They have been characterised on the basis of infrared spectral measurements, elemental analyses and magnetic susceptibility data. The polymeric nature of the products has been indicated by their molecular weights. The coordination of phosphite units to metal atom of the other molecule through phosphoryl oxygen gave rise to O-P-O-bridges.

WORK on metal derivatives of dialkyl phosphites reported from these laboratories¹⁻⁵, has been extended to niobium(V) and tantalum(V) derivatives in the present paper. Survey of the literature on the reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chlorides with organo-phosphorus compounds, reveals that no work has been reported on such reactions so far. In view of this it was thought of interest to study the reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chlorides with dialkyl/diaryl phosphites in different molar ratios and varying conditions of temperature and solvent.

Experimental

Reagents: Niobium(V) chloride (Fluka) and tantalum(V) chloride (Fluka) were used as such after analysis. Diethyl phosphite (Fluka), di-isopropyl phosphite (Aldrich), di-*n*-butyl phosphite (Fluka) and diphenyl phosphite (Aldrich) were distilled before use. Benzene was dried as before²⁻⁵. All manipulations were carried out using standard joints and glass apparatus with rigorous exclusion of moisture.

Analysis: Phosphorus and chlorine were estimated as usual²⁻⁵. The molecular weight of the compounds were determined using Gallenkamp Semi-micro ebulliometer in benzene solvent. Magnetic susceptibility of the products was determined using Gouy's balance. Infrared spectra (near and far) were recorded on Beckman spectrophotometer model IR-20 in nujol or neat as required.

Reactions of niobium(V) chloride and tantalum(V) chloride with dialkyl/diaryl phosphites in different molar ratios:

(a) **In benzene solvent:** To a known amount of the metal chloride in benzene was added the calculated

amount of dialkyl / diaryl phosphite in benzene under dry conditions. On adding the dialkyl / diaryl phosphite heat and hydrogen chloride were evolved in every case. The colour of reaction mixture changed from yellow to orange with different phosphites. The reaction mixture was refluxed at an oil bath temperature of 100-110° and under reduced pressure (~20 mm) for about 40-60 hrs in each case till evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The excess of benzene was distilled off and its traces were removed under vacuo (1-2 mm) at 80°. Viscous liquid or solid products were obtained.

The physical state, colour, amount and analytical results of the products are given in Table 1.

(b) **Without solvent:** To a weighed amount of the metal(V) chloride in dry flask was added the calculated amount of dialkyl / diaryl phosphite under anhydrous conditions. Excess of heat and hydrogen chloride were evolved in the reactions. On shaking yellowish or orangish paste was obtained. The contents of the flask were heated at an oil bath temperature of 110-120° and reduced pressure (~20 mm). The pasty mass solidified after 2-3 hrs and was further heated till evolution of hydrogen chloride. In case of diphenyl phosphite the products were viscous liquids whereas in other cases yellowish white solid products were formed. Some reactions were complete in 2-3 hrs while the others took 12-15 hrs for completion. Solid products were washed with dry benzene and dried under vacuo (1-2 mm) at 80°. Analytical results with other properties are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of niobium(V) chloride and tantalum(V) chloride with dialkyl phosphites (Et-, Pr^t-, Buⁿ- and Ph-) have been carried out in different molar

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TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF NIOBIUM(V) AND TANTALUM(V) DERIVATIVES

S.No.	Reactants		Compound Colour, state & yield (g)	Found (Calcd.)				Molecular weight
	MCl ₅ (g)	Dialkyl/diaryl phosphites (g)		% Cl	% P	% C	% H	
*1 _a	1.87	3.31	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂ Orange vis liquid (4.68)	16.19 (16.01)	9.44 (9.31)	42.91 (43.25)	3.12 (3.01)	700 (665.4)
2 _a	1.80	3.36	NbCl ₅ [OP(O)(OC ₆ H ₅)] [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂ Orange vis liquid (4.35)	12.39 (12.82)	11.19 (11.21)	35.20 (37.07)	3.12 (2.71)	862.60 (665.40)
*3 _b	1.71	4.59	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Orange vis liquid (5.76)	9.70 (9.31)	11.75 (12.19)	56.28 (56.60)	3.58 (3.92)	1966 (862.9)
4 _b	1.70	4.51	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Orange vis liquid (5.37)	9.44 (9.31)	11.56 (12.19)	55.28 (56.60)	3.95 (3.92)	—
*5 _c	1.97	7.61	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₄ Orange vis liquid (8.71)	3.90 (3.34)	11.78 (11.69)	54.08 (54.41)	4.25 (3.76)	—
6 _c	1.43	5.25	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₄ Orange vis liquid (6.04)	4.20 (3.34)	12.40 (11.69)	53.98 (54.41)	4.07 (3.76)	—
*7 _d	1.52	6.82	Nb [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₅ Orange vis liquid (7.79)	1.01 (nil)	12.13 (12.29)	56.98 (57.28)	4.05 (3.97)	—
8 _d	1.67	7.43	Nb [P(O)(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₅ Orange vis liquid (8.20)	1.21 (nil)	12.30 (12.29)	57.34 (57.28)	4.55 (3.97)	—
*9 _e	1.46	1.58	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (2.11)	22.37 (22.49)	12.33 (13.00)	16.36 (16.11)	4.80 (5.30)	—
10 _e	1.19	1.35	NbCl ₅ [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (1.33)	9.14 (10.30)	18.21 (17.93)	15.74 (13.93)	2.52 (2.90)	—
*11 _f	1.85	3.07	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (3.57)	13.37 (12.36)	15.40 (16.18)	—	—	—
12 _f	1.61	2.64	Nb [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ White solid	0.94 (nil)	19.10 (20.80)	21.68 (21.53)	3.16 (4.47)	—
*13 _g	1.95	4.29	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₄ White solid (3.74)	4.99 (5.25)	19.00 (18.30)	—	—	—
14 _g	1.57	3.55	Nb [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₅)] [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish white solid (3.20)	0.87 (nil)	18.55 (20.78)	—	—	—
*15 _h	1.96	5.55	Nb [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₅ White solid (6.24)	1.10 (nil)	20.37 (19.90)	—	—	—
16 _h	1.77	5.20	Nb [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₅ White solid (4.06)	0.71 (nil)	18.53 (19.90)	—	—	—
*17 _i	1.44	1.86	NbCl ₅ [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₇)] [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₂ Yellowish solid (2.25)	16.26 (15.78)	13.65 (13.74)	—	—	—
18 _i	1.05	1.33	NbCl ₅ [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₇)] ₃ Yellowish solid (1.85)	9.88 (9.50)	16.56 (16.67)	—	—	—
*19 _j	1.43	2.78	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (1.52)	10.56 (10.79)	13.71 (14.11)	—	—	—
20 _j	1.41	2.82	Nb [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₃ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₃ White solid (1.87)	1.41 (nil)	19.32 (18.50)	—	—	—
*21 _k	1.46	3.85	NbCl ₅ [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₄ Yellowish solid (3.92)	3.70 (4.50)	15.60 (17.46)	—	—	—
22 _k	1.64	4.14	Nb [OP(O)(OC ₂ H ₇)] [P(O)(OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (2.54)	1.70 (nil)	16.26 (17.46)	—	—	—

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PURI & SINGH : METAL DERIVATIVES OF ORGANO-PHOSPHORUS COMPOUNDS. PART II : ETC.

S.No.	Reactants		Compound Colour, state & yield (g)	Found (Calcd.)				Molecular weight
	MCl ₅ (g)	Dialkyl/diaryl phosphites (g)		% Cl	% P	% C	% H	
*23 _a	1.53	4.94	Nb [P(O) (OC ₈ H ₇) ₃] ₅ White solid (3.89)	1.12 (nil)	16.41 (16.89)	—	—	—
24 _a	1.56	4.95	Nb [P(O) (OC ₈ H ₇) ₃] ₅ Yellow solid (4.50)	0.25 (nil)	17.20 (16.89)	—	—	—
*25 _a	1.78	2.59	NbCl ₃ [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (3.82)	19.61 (18.20)	10.07 (10.59)	—	—	—
26 _a	1.11	1.14	NbCl [OP(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₃ Yellow solid (1.53)	9.86 (8.86)	14.42 (15.40)	—	—	—
*27 _b	2.11	4.56	NbCl [OP(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₃ White solid (5.51)	5.30 (5.40)	14.16 (14.20)	—	—	—
28 _b	1.79	4.15	Nb [OP(OC ₄ H ₉) (O)] ₂ [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₃ White solid (3.56)	1.12 (nil)	16.94 (16.67)	—	—	—
*29 _o	1.81	5.53	NbCl [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₄ White solid (3.99)	3.53 (3.96)	12.91 (13.70)	—	—	—
30 _o	1.69	4.91	Nb [OP(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₃ White solid (3.70)	1.03 (nil)	15.24 (15.35)	—	—	—
*31 _a	2.06	7.49	Nb [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₅ White solid (6.08)	0.98 (nil)	14.83 (14.63)	—	—	—
32 _a	1.52	5.90	Nb [P(O) (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂] ₅ White solid (3.32)	1.04 (nil)	14.50 (14.63)	—	—	—
*33 _a	1.83	2.44	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish vis liquid (3.99)	15.24 (14.16)	7.91 (8.22)	—	—	—
34 _a	1.95	2.58	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish vis liquid (4.06)	14.69 (14.16)	7.55 (8.22)	—	—	—
*35 _b	1.87	3.73	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish vis liquid (5.16)	13.24 (14.16)	8.67 (8.22)	—	—	—
36 _b	1.51	3.03	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish vis liquid (3.99)	14.10 (14.16)	8.50 (8.22)	—	—	—
*37 _o	1.83	4.85	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish vis liquid (6.12)	6.82 (7.46)	8.97 (9.77)	—	—	—
38 _o	1.75	4.59	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish vis liquid (5.82)	6.65 (3.04)	8.89 (9.77)	—	—	—
*39 _a	2.17	7.18	TaCl [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₄ Yellowish vis liquid (8.21)	2.47 (3.04)	10.94 (11.51)	—	—	3596 (1148.4)
40 _a	2.21	7.32	TaCl [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₄ Yellowish vis liquid (8.26)	3.12 (3.04)	11.30 (11.51)	—	—	—
*41 _a	2.27	1.92	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (3.17)	19.63 (18.97)	10.21 (11.02)	—	—	—
42 _a	1.75	1.41	TaCl ₅ [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (2.21)	13.68 (14.29)	12.33 (12.47)	—	—	—
*43	2.44	2.86	TaCl ₅ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (4.06)	10.38 (10.71)	13.30 (14.03)	—	—	—
44 _b	2.25	2.72	Ta [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (2.72)	nil (nil)	16.85 (17.42)	—	—	—
*45 _o	2.38	3.76	TaCl [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₄ Yellowish solid (5.20)	5.04 (4.64)	15.73 (16.22)	—	—	—

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S.No.	Reactants		Compound Colour, state & yield (g)	Found (Calcd)				Molecular weight
	MCl ₅ (g)	Dialkyl/diaryl phosphites (g)		% Cl	% P	% C	% H	
46 _c	2.43	3.94	Ta [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (4.41)	nil (nil)	16.56 (17.70)	-	-	-
*47 _a	2.71	5.37	Ta Cl [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₂ White solid (3.71)	5.86 (5.92)	14.82 (15.52)	-	-	-
48 _d	2.29	4.53	Ta [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₅ White solid (3.29)	nil (nil)	16.56 (17.95)	-	-	-
*49 _a	1.66	1.56	TaCl ₃ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₂ Yellowish white solid (2.52)	16.83 (17.25)	9.99 (10.04)	-	-	-
50 _a	1.63	1.58	TaCl ₃ [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] Yellowish solid (2.15)	12.54 (13.15)	11.19 (11.50)	-	-	-
*51 _b	1.28	1.79	TaCl ₃ [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] Yellowish solid (2.49)	13.49 (13.15)	10.65 (11.50)	-	-	-
52 _b	1.77	2.53	TaCl [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₂ Yellowish solid (2.39)	4.75 (5.30)	13.43 (13.90)	-	-	-
*53 _c	2.07	3.95	TaCl ₂ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (4.29)	9.01 (9.50)	12.72 (12.45)	-	-	-
54 _c	1.91	3.65	Ta [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₃ Yellowish solid (3.05)	nil (nil)	16.89 (16.26)	-	-	-
*55 _a	2.27	5.34	TaCl ₃ [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] Yellowish solid (6.52)	12.74 (13.15)	11.04 (11.50)	-	-	3459 (1005.90)
56 _a	2.13	4.49	Ta [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₇) ₂] ₅ Yellowish solid (3.82)	nil (nil)	15.70 (15.35)	-	-	-
*57 _a	1.78	2.11	TaCl ₃ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₂ Yellowish solid (2.54)	15.02 (15.81)	9.97 (9.20)	-	-	-
58 _a	1.41	1.68	TaCl [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] Yellowish solid (1.66)	7.12 (7.26)	13.50 (12.71)	-	-	-
*59 _b	1.76	2.89	TaCl ₃ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₂ Yellowish solid (4.35)	15.30 (15.81)	9.78 (9.20)	-	-	-
60 _b	1.46	2.51	TaCl [OP(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₂ Yellowish solid (2.09)	4.58 (4.80)	11.48 (12.62)	-	-	-
*61 _c	1.35	2.99	TaCl ₃ [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₂ Yellowish solid (3.92)	15.65 (15.81)	9.29 (9.20)	-	-	-
62 _c	1.67	3.68	TaCl [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₄ Yellowish solid (2.46)	3.21 (3.58)	11.88 (12.53)	-	-	-
*63 _d	1.51	4.47	Ta [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₅ White solid (3.50)	nil (nil)	13.37 (13.52)	-	-	-
64 _d	1.46	4.26	Ta [P(O) (OC ₂ H ₉) ₂] ₅ Yellowish solid (3.40)	nil (nil)	13.61 (13.52)	-	-	-

* Reactions carried out in solvent benzene and the rest without using any solvent.

a - Molar ratio 1 : 2 ; b - 1 : 3 ; c - 1 : 4 and d - 1 : 5.

ratios in refluxing benzene as well as without using any solvent at higher temperature and under reduced pressure to avoid side reactions. The reactions were exothermic and faster in the absence of any solvent. Reactions with niobium(V) chloride were faster than those with tantalum(V) chloride.

The products were fairly moisture sensitive and became sticky upon exposure to the atmosphere. Niobium(V) complexes with diphenyl phosphite were bright orange sticky and viscous liquids while those with other dialkyl phosphites (Et-, Pr^t- and Buⁿ-) were yellowish solids. In the beginning some of the products were viscous liquids which solidified on standing for some days. Diphenyl phosphite derivatives of tantalum were yellow oily sticky liquids whereas its diethyl, di-isopropyl and di-*n*-butyl phosphite derivatives were white or yellowish white solids. The solid products were insoluble in common organic solvents while liquid products were soluble in benzene.

The products obtained in 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4 and 1 : 5 molar ratio reactions were $MCl_3[P(O)(OR)_2]_2$, (I); $MCl_2[OP(O)(OR)]_2[P(O)(OR)_2]$, (II); $MCl[OP(O)(OR)]_2$, (III); $MCl_2[P(O)(OR)_2]_3$, (IV); $MCl[OP(O)(OR)]_2[P(O)(OR)_2]$, (V); $M[OP(O)(OR)]_2[P(O)(OR)_2]$, (VI); $MCl[P(O)(OR)_2]_4$, (VII); $M[OP(O)(OR)]_2[P(O)(OR)_2]_3$, (VIII) and $M[P(O)(OR)_2]_5$, (IX). The amount of reactants, yield, colour and analytical results of the isolated products have been given in Table 1.

The reactions in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 gave products, the elemental analysis of which did not agree with the expected analysis. However, in some cases of niobium compounds, the analysis tallied with the formula $NbO[P(O)(OR)_2]Cl_2$ suggesting that two chlorine atoms have been replaced by an oxygen atom. It has been reported in the literature that niobium(V) halides have greater tendency of oxygen abstraction⁸⁻⁹. It is therefore possible that in such reactions oxygen abstraction takes place.

In case of reactions of tantalum(V) chloride with dialkyl phosphites in benzene solvent only three chlorine atoms are replaced with diethyl phosphite while all the five chlorine atoms are replaced with other phosphites. Further replacement of chlorine is very slow and required longer periods of refluxing. On the other hand, in the absence of any solvent, the reaction proceeded well with the removal of all the chlorine atoms when the reaction was carried out even in the molar ratio of 1 : 5.

The infrared spectra of these compounds showed strong absorption maxima in the region 1200-1100 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to phosphoryl stretching mode of vibrations. The bathochromic shift from 1265 cm^{-1} , for free phosphoryl group^{10,11}, could be due to

coordination of phosphoryl oxygen of phosphite units to the metal atom of adjacent molecule. Sharp, medium sharp and broad bands were observed near 1010 cm^{-1} and 530 cm^{-1} and P-Ph linkages absorb in this region. A sharp absorption band near 600 cm^{-1} could be assigned to P-O-Ph linkage which is differentiated from P-Ph absorption near 530 cm^{-1} . Occurrence of sharp, medium sharp, broad and weak sharp bands, in the region 1170-1030 cm^{-1} could be assigned to $\nu(P)-O-C$ vibrations and sharp and medium sharp bands in the 950-730 cm^{-1} could be due to P-O-(C) linkages. The absorption bands in the region 980-930 cm^{-1} could be associated with $\nu Nb-O$ vibrations^{8,12} and weak absorption bands in 890-850 cm^{-1} region could be assigned to Ta-O linkage. Very sharp bands were observed in 730-710 cm^{-1} range and were assigned to $\nu P-C$ absorptions. In the complexes, other than 1 : 5 and having no chlorine, absorption bands (br, wsh) were observed in 330-360 cm^{-1} region and could be assigned to Nb-Cl bond. An absorption band (ms, w) near 460 cm^{-1} was assigned to Ta-Cl linkage.

In all the reactions of Nb(V) and Ta(V) chloride with dialkyl phosphites presumably an addition compound is first formed after which hydrogen chloride and alkyl chloride respectively are liberated. The presence of phosphorus to carbon linkage (as shown by ir spectra) suggest that an internal rearrangement of molecule takes place.

The molecular weight of soluble compounds in boiling benzene (Table 1) showed tendency towards polymerization.

Niobium(V) complexes show a slight paramagnetism (0.37 B.M. to 0.90 B.M.) which is in agreement with results reported earlier¹³ and is probably due to temperature independent second order Zeeman-effect as suggested by Fowles *et al*¹⁴.

The products did not melt but were decomposed to blue-black mass in all cases in the temperature range 230-250° probably due to the reduction of Nb(V) to a blue Nb(III) ion^{15,16} by phosphite.

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